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VIBRATION FREQUENCY DESIGN AND STUDY OF COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

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00

Introduction

Dynamic Characteristics

1. Frequency of Beam-type Vibration
2. Shape of Nodal Line
3. Modal Node Position

Fuselage

Stiffened Cylindrical Shell
(composite material)

Key Words

1. Initial Stage
2. Stiffness Design

01

Equivalent Stiffness Model

Equivalent Stiffness Model

- ① Geosim model
- ② Limited Design parameters
- ③ Similar stiffness characteristics

$$\frac{f_M}{f_R} = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{E_M I_M / L_M^3}{M_M}}{\frac{E_R I_R / L_R^3}{M_R}}}$$

$$K_{Ri} = \sqrt{\frac{E_R I_{Ri}}{\rho_R A_{Ri} L_R + M_{KR}}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Mi}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}}$$

Optimize the equivalent stiffness model

Discuss the influence of Material Parameters

Design & Verification

01

Equivalent Stiffness Model

Target Frequency Values of fuselage & Model

Frequency	F7	F8	F10	F11
Target Frequency fuselage (cycles/time)	140	150	280	305
Frequency of Model(cycles/time)	2100	2250	4200	4575

01

Equivalent Stiffness Model

$K_{Ri(x/z)}$ is defined as the stiffness index of the fuselage structure

$$K_{Rix} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miy}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}}$$

$$K_{Riz} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miz}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M}}$$

Fuselage Stiffness Index

02

Influence of Material Parameters

The influence of anisotropy material on the beam-type vibration of fuselage can't be neglected.

Correlations among the parameters of anisotropic cylindrical shell and frequencies are discussed

Developing a design method to ensure the dynamic index of the composite fuselage and target values are within acceptable limits

Influence of Material Parameters

$$\begin{cases} L_{11}u + L_{12}v + L_{13}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \\ L_{21}u + L_{22}v + L_{23}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} \\ L_{31}u + L_{32}v + L_{33}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \end{cases}$$

$$[P] \begin{Bmatrix} u_{mn} \\ v_{mn} \\ w_{mn} \end{Bmatrix} = \rho h \begin{bmatrix} \omega^2 & & \\ & \omega^2 & \\ & & \omega^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_{mn} \\ v_{mn} \\ w_{mn} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\omega_{beam}^2 = \frac{EI}{\rho A} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L} \right)^4$$

$$\Omega_{beam}^2 = \frac{\rho R^2 (1 - \nu_x \cdot \nu_\theta)}{E_x} \omega_{beam}^2$$

02

Influence of Material Parameters

02

Influence of Material Parameters

Equation	$y = A1 * \exp(-x/t1) + y0$		
Adj. R-Squa	0.93633	0.95121	
		Value	Standard Err
Error2	y0	-0.86384	0.06196
Error2	A1	0.96827	0.06522
Error2	t1	-100193.054	5688.11783
Eoor1	y0	-0.99601	0.06056
Eoor1	A1	1.10663	0.06384
Eoor1	t1	-97961.7790	4730.94596

02

Influence of Material Parameters

Equation	$y = A1 * \exp(-x/t1) + A2 * \exp(-x/t2) + y0$		
Adj. R-Square	0.99052	0.96246	
		Value	Standard Error
Error1	y0	3.0241	0.28918
Error1	A1	-0.58773	0.03638
Error1	t1	0.56146	0.05731
Error1	A2	-3.13137	0.25026
Error1	t2	9.19223	1.37952
Error2	y0	3.39132	1.081
Error2	A1	-0.64667	0.05042
Error2	t1	0.53719	0.07801
Error2	A2	-3.39742	1.02543
Error2	t2	14.10973	6.16103

03

Verification

Comparisons between Equivalent Stiffness Model (red) & Fuselage Structure (black)

03

Verification

Comparisons between Target & Calculated Frequency

Frequency	Target value (cycles/time)	Calculated value (cycles/time)	Relative Error
F7	140	138.49	-1.08%
F8	150	149.91	-0.06%
10	280	268.90	-3.96%
F11	305	277.73	-8.94%

03

Verification

Comparisons between Target & Calculated Modal Node Position

Position of Modal Nodes	Target value(mm)	Calculation value(mm)	Error value
7S1	920	902	-0.45%
7S2	3080	3098	0.45%
8S1	890	872	-0.45%
8S2	3120	3137	0.43%
10S1	490	495	0.13%
10S2	2000	2010	0.25%
10S3	3510	3514	0.10%
11S1	500	500	0.00%
11S2	1990	2000	0.25%
11S3	3480	3490	0.25%

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